

IEEE World Forum
on Internet of Things

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Hybrid: In-Person and Virtual

Sustainability and the Internet of Things

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Augmenting first responders' senses with Edge AI

Inside a fire engine

Presented by QUOTE.COM

Design & research by ANIMAGRAFFS

A fire engine (also referred to as a "pumper") transports crew, supplies, and firefighting capabilities to the scene of an incident.

Warning lights

Upper level lights, like the light bar on the cab roof, are for long distance warning. Lower level lights on the sides, fenders, and bumpers are for close proximity warning.

Master stream

An engine-mounted master stream is capable of delivering huge amounts of water over long distances.

Hoses

Various diameters and lengths of hoses are stored throughout the apparatus.

Electronic sirens

The electronic siren uses a loud speaker to produce warning sounds.

Preconnect

A pre-connected hose reduces preparation steps at the scene.

Air horns

Air horns use compressed air to create a loud warning sound.

Extended front bumper

Spacious front bumpers provide convenient access to essential tools and connections, especially in confined environments like small streets where only the front of the engine can face the scene.

Storage compartments

The apparatus has ample storage space for essential firefighting tools and implements.

Pump

The pump is powered by the diesel engine through the drive shaft.

Exterior paint

Retroreflective paint stripes on the sides and chevron markings at the rear are required by regulation. Retroreflective materials reflect light back to the source for high visibility.

Federal Q siren

The Federal Q is a traditional electro-mechanical siren (sound is produced by an electrically driven metal rotor) that produces a characteristic "wail" sound. It's controlled by a driver-side left foot switch in this instance.

How can I T help?

Theresa Chong, “Futuristic Firefighter Suit Has Sensors, Head-up Display Futuristic firefighter gear integrates vital-sign sensors and indoor tracking”

IEEE SPECTRUM, 19 SEP 2014

Future Fire: Motorola's Next Generation Fireground Communications system includes a helmet-mounted camera, a head-up display on the breathing mask, an environmental sensor, a strap that monitors vital signs, indoor location tracking, and a rugged radio.
PHOTO: MOTOROLA SOLUTIONS

edge
How can AIoT help?

RESCUER

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 833507

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Extending human physiology

T-shirt
The BM goes here

Environmental Module

Temperature
Humidity
CO

Magnetic Connector

Magnetic Cable

PTFE Filter

ON/OFF Switch

Abstract architecture of Data Fusion model based on a deep Neural Network architecture for cough detection.

Evangelos Katsadouros, Panagiotis Kasnesis, Dimitrios G. Kogias, Charalampos Z. Patrikakis, Alexios Vlachopoulos, Aspasia Tzeletopoulou, Harris Georgiou, "Smart textiles and biometrics/movement data fusion in deep learning for Search and Rescue operations – FASTER (EU Horizon 2020)", SafeThessaloniki 2022 – 9th International Conference on Civil Protection & New Technologies 29 September-1 October, Thessaloniki International Fair

1. Recommend evacuation
2. Recommend stop
3. Fire
4. Emergency contained
5. Distress

Rescuers are not only humans!

The wearable can be used for:
Geolocating the animal
Bark Detection
Activity Recognition

Kasnesis, P.; Doulgerakis, V.; Uzunidis, D.; Kogias, D.G.; Funcia, S.I.; González, M.B.; Giannousis, C.; Patrikakis, C.Z. Deep Learning Empowered Wearable-Based Behavior Recognition for Search and Rescue Dogs. *Sensors* 2022, 22, 993.

interested in details?

IoT and First Responders

Fri. Nov 11, 2022

8:00 AM - 10:00 AM

Thank you!
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